

PRODUCTION AND EVALUATION OF TRIO PANCAKE MIX

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Production and Evaluation of TRIO Pancake Mix

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Abstract

The main objective of this paper was to determine the production and evaluation of TRIO (Jackfruit Seeds, Sweet Potato, and Taro Flours) Pancake Mix with 30%, 40%, and 50% proportions to the pancake consumers, pancake sellers and pancake makers who live in Pasig City. Experimental method of research was utilized with survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument. This study also used the nine Hedonic rating scale for the evaluation and five Likert scale for the production of TRIO Pancake Mix. The result of the TRIO Pancake Mix physiochemical analysis showed that the developed product contains the following: (a) 4.86 mg of iron per 100 g ;(b) 80.8 g of carbohydrates of 100 g; (c) a pH of 6.99 at 20.3 °C; (d) 3.49 g moisture per 100g; and (e) a lead content of 0.25** µg/g. In addition, The evaluations of the production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand of the TRIO Pancake Mix of 30%, 40%, and 50% proportion are mostly Very High Potential (VHP) since the ingredients are affordable and competitive in price, available locally all year round, and can meet the demands of the consumers. To further improve the product, comments and suggestions were given by the respondents.

Keywords: *production, evaluation, pancake mix, marketability*

Introduction

According to Linden (2023) for the Smithsonian Magazine, pancakes are one of the earliest foods prepared by humanity. “Flat cakes”, or earlier versions of pancakes, have been made by stone age people mixing flour from ferns and cattails and water to be baked on a hot rock. Currently, pancakes have become an easy-to-cook food.

This study is rooted from the fact that nowadays most meals are pre-made and instant. This is to keep up with our fast-paced, modern lives. However, the problem with instant food is that most are not as nutritious and beneficial as freshly prepared meals. High consumption of pre-made and instant food has an increased health risk to the body due to preservatives and other chemicals. Instant foods are also high in sodium content as a result of processing procedures. When an excessive amount of sodium is consumed, numerous health issues may occur, such as hypertension, kidney diseases, and cardiovascular diseases (Zhang et al., 2021).

DepEd Order 13 s.2017 entitled “Policy and Guidelines on Healthy Food and Beverage Choices in Schools and in DepEd Offices” also states that a healthy and balanced diet is important in the development of children, contributing to improved mood and cognitive function. Emphasized in the issue is the assurance that children have access to healthy and nutritious food (DepEd, 2024). Thus, the researcher, aiming to find a healthier alternative for instant foods, explored the possibility of innovating pancakes by combining three different flours namely, jackfruit seed, sweet potato, and taro for producing a TRIO Pancake Mix. The researcher chose these ingredients for their health benefits. Additionally, they are also convenient to prepare, cost effective, locally available, and sustainable.

Artocarpus heterophyllus is known to be a healthy fruit, and its seeds are described as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antidiabetic (Khan et al., 2021). Despite the nutritional benefits of jackfruit seeds, however, they are considered an underutilized part of the fruit. This is due to the difficulty of processing and storing of the seeds, resulting in large amounts of jackfruit waste. These can contribute to food waste, causing environmental problems (Kalse & Swami, 2022).

The researcher also studied the addition of two more flours to the jackfruit flour, namely sweet potato and taro flours as they are highly nutritious. For example, sweet potatoes are rich in fiber, Vitamin A, and beta-carotene (Pelegriano, 2021). On the other hand, taro is rich in vitamin C, vitamin B6, and vitamin E as well as manganese, potassium, copper, phosphorus, and folate (WebMD, 2022).

Addition of sweet potato and taro flours to the jackfruit flour will enhance the color, flavor, and texture of the product. Sweet potato flour is a good replacement for flour due to its gluten-free nature, as well as its use as a thickening agent (Walsh, 2023). Taro flour, on the other hand, is being used as an additional ingredient for different food items such as in bread rolls, chips, and even beer (Ferdaus et al., 2023).

A pancake mix from jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro flours will be a food product that is convenient and, at the same time, healthy. This product can also be considered value-added as the jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro adds nutritional value and quality to the normal pancake mix.

Research Questions

The main objective of this paper was to determine the production and evaluation of TRIO (Jackfruit Seeds, Sweet Potato, and Taro Flours) Pancake Mix with 30%, 40%, and 50% proportions to the pancake consumers, pancake sellers and pancake makers who live in Pasig City. More specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. How can a pancake mixture be produced using jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro flours?
2. What is the physicochemical analysis of the TRIO Pancake Mix in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. iron;
 - 2.2. carbohydrates;
 - 2.3. ph level;
 - 2.4. moisture content; and
 - 2.5. lead content?
3. What is the evaluation of pancake consumers, sellers, and makers of the TRIO Pancake in terms of the following criteria:
 - 3.1. appearance;
 - 3.2. color;
 - 3.3. aroma;
 - 3.4. taste; and
 - 3.5. texture?
4. Are there any significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents of the TRIO Pancake Mix utilizing the three different proportions in terms of the aforementioned criteria?
5. What is the evaluation of pancake consumers, sellers, and makers on the production of TRIO Pancake Mix utilizing the three proportions in terms of the following:
 - 5.1. production cost;
 - 5.2. supply availability; and
 - 5.3. consumer demand?
6. Are there any significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents in the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix in terms of the forementioned criteria?
7. What are the comments and suggestions given to the prepared pancake mix?

Literature Review

The term “pancake” was used during the 15th century and became standard in 19th century America. Previously, people called them Indian cakes, hoe cakes, johnnycakes, journey cakes, buckwheat cakes, griddle cakes, and flapjacks. Early American pancakes were made with buckwheat or cornmeal. It was even said that Thomas Jefferson loved pancakes so much that he sent a special recipe from the White House to his hometown (Nayeem, 2022).

Based on the National Nutrition Council’s article All about pancakes (2023), in the Philippines, pancakes are not just for breakfast. There are a lot of stories about pancakes being sold during snack time or what Filipinos call merienda near schools and workplaces. People love pancakes because of their sweet and buttery flavor but must be consumed moderately. Pancakes are high in sugar and fat that could cause high blood pressure and diabetes mellitus.

In this day and age, pancakes have become an easy-to-cook food, according to Linden (2023). However, the base recipe has been modified to include eggs, milk, and raising agents (e.g., baking powder), and a fluffy, patty-shaped cake is produced from the batter. Additionally, different ways of cooking pancake batter have been observed in different countries, resulting in different varieties of the pancake recipe. However, the flat shape of the pancake varieties remains the same.

Considered as the largest fruit tree in the world, the jackfruit tree produces the fruit *Artocarpus heterophyllus* which is commonly known as jackfruit. Native to the western coast of India, this tree is distributed along tropical and subtropical areas such as in Malaysia, Brazil, and the Philippines (Rao, 2020).

This fruit also contains various nutrients. Health benefits of this fruit allow it to be antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antidiabetic, and anthelmintic (Khan et al., 2021). According to Krupa et al. (2022), jackfruit seeds contain: carbohydrates; proteins, such as arginine and leucine; vitamins, such as vitamin C and B-complex group (e.g., vitamin B6, riboflavin, and niacin); minerals such as magnesium and calcium; and fiber.

Meanwhile, sweet potatoes, or scientifically known as *Ipomoea batatas* (L.), are considered as one of the most important crops here in the Philippines. They are commonly served as merienda and cooked in different ways such as sweet potato fries and chips. These crops are also known for their nutritional value, as they can help manage diabetes. This is because, unlike starchy food, their low glycemic index scale allows the slow release of sugar into the bloodstream. The fiber content in sweet potatoes also helps in improving digestion, promoting a healthy digestive tract. High levels of Vitamin A and beta-carotene sweet potatoes can be sourced from sweet potatoes, helping to prevent Vitamin A deficiency (Pelegriano, 2021).

Sweet potatoes may also be utilized as sweet potato flour. The process of creating flour from sweet potatoes includes dicing washed and peeled raw sweet potatoes, drying the sweet potatoes at a certain temperature, and grinding them. The resulting flour has a longer shelf life than fresh sweet potatoes and is even considered to be an ingredient easy to add in different foods. Sweet potato flour is said to add a sweet taste but is low in protein content. This is why xanthan gum (or another stabilizer) are added, which are also added in other gluten-free flours. However, it is noted that sweet potato flour is more expensive than other healthy flour in the market (Walsh,

2023).

Likewise, Taro (*Colocasia esculenta*), or locally known as gabi, is a crop rich in starch and dietary fibers. Taro is also an important part of Solomon Island, specifically, due to its part in their diet and customs. In the Philippines, taro is more than just a crop as it is considered a vital source of food and for its domestic purposes. Furthermore, taro cultivation has been noted by the UN Food and Agriculture Organization as a way to alleviate food scarcity and improve the livelihood of low-income households (Onsay et al., 2023).

In the study conducted by Arici, et al (2020), the use of taro flour as a substitute to wheat flour and gluten free flour increased and strengthened the effect on dough structure. It also increased the starch resistance of the dough. Dietary fiber content also increased significantly when taro flour was added in both formulations.

Furthermore, according to the study conducted by Meng, et al (2022), it has been shown that replacing wheat flour with potato or sweet potato flour fortifies its nutritional value. It also showed that it improves the properties of the flour, and dough, and the texture and sensory quality of the bread.

Methodology

Research Design

For this study, the experimental method of research was utilized since it was a useful tool for studying and understanding the effects of mixing ingredients when formulating food products (Squeo et al., 2021). In this case, the proportions of TRIO pancake mix were manipulated in order to see if there are significant differences based on appearance, color, taste, texture, and so on. The researcher considered an experimental method of research appropriate for evaluating the TRIO Pancake Mix in terms of appearance, color, aroma, taste, texture, and its marketability.

Respondents

The data that was gathered in this research came from the thirty (30) Pancake Consumers, thirty (30) Pancake Sellers, and thirty (30) Pancake Makers of Pasig City during the school year 2023-2024.

Instrument

A questionnaire containing a 9-Point Hedonic Scale and 5-Point Likert Scale surveying tool was used for the evaluation of the TRIO Pancake Mix. This questionnaire was validated by 3 food experts, 1 statistician, 1 grammarian.

The 9-Point Hedonic Scale is the most widely used scale for measuring food acceptability. The reliability, validity, and discriminative ability of the scale was proven in food acceptance. The 9-Point Hedonic Scale in this study is for the evaluation of TRIO Pancake Mix with regards to its appearance, color, aroma, taste, and texture.

Procedure

The produced TRIO Pancake Mix was subjected to physicochemical analysis through the services of F.A.S.T (The First Analytical Services and Technical Cooperative) Laboratories. All requests which will need approval were accomplished before conducting the analysis. In evaluating the TRIO Pancake Mix, a validated survey questionnaire was used. To further validate the results of the questionnaire, a statistician was consulted.

Respondents were gathered, and a taste test of the cooked TRIO Pancake Mix was conducted. There were three versions of pancakes presented: 30%, 40%, and 50% proportions of jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro flours. A questionnaire was given to each respondent to complete. Once all questionnaires were collected, the data was tallied, tabulated, and underwent statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation.

Ethical Considerations

Before starting the study by collaborating with the respondents, the researcher went over and explained the objective of the study. Along with a letter encouraging respondents to complete the necessary questionnaire voluntarily and thoroughly, the researcher also provided a consent document for the study. The data collected from the respondents would remain the most private and confidential and only be utilized for the purpose of the study. As such, the researcher had considered protecting the privacy of the respondents and others. This was done in compliance with RA 10173, also referred to as the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Results and Discussion

Production of TRIO Pancake Mix

A standard pancake recipe was innovated to produce a TRIO pancake mix utilizing three different flours from jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro. An experimental method was done for the making of the three flours used as substitute to the wheat flour used in the standard recipe.

Physicochemical Analysis of the TRIO Pancake Mix in terms of Iron, Carbohydrates, pH level, Moisture content and Lead

content

The result of the TRIO Pancake Mix physiochemical analysis showed that the product made contains the following: (a) 4.86 mg of iron per 100 g, which is lower than the recommended 8 mg and 27 mg for males and females, respectively; (b) 80.8 g of carbohydrates of 100 g, which is considered moderately high content and indicate that it has nutritional value and potentially beneficial to the consumer; (c) a pH of 6.99 at 20.3 °C, which is slightly acidic but very close to neutral, having minimal impact on most biological or chemical processes that are sensitive to pH changes; (d) 3.49 g moisture per 100g, which is considered moderate moisture content and could indicate little change of microbial fungal growth; and (e) a lead content of 0.25** µg/g, indicating that the lead content is below detection threshold or it is considered a safe amount for its intended use.

Evaluation of Consumers, Sellers, and Makers of the TRIO Pancake Mix For 30% Proportion

Table 1. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% Proportion regarding Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a distinct appearance.	7.80	VA	7.93	VA	7.90	VA
2. It is free from lumps.	8.00	VA	8.33	VA	7.87	VA
3. It looks tender and easy to bite.	8.67	EA	8.50	EA	8.17	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.16	VA	8.26	VA	7.98	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 30% proportion in terms of its appearance is Very Acceptable (AV) with the weighted mean value of 8.16 from the consumers, 8.26 from the makers, and 7.98 from the sellers.

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% Proportion regarding Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable aroma	8.50	EA	8.10	VA	8.00	VA
2. It has a sweeter and freshly made smell	8.23	VA	8.27	VA	8.00	VA
3. It has buttery aroma	8.20	VA	8.17	VA	8.00	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.18	VA	8.00	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 30% proportion in terms of its aroma is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.31 from the consumers, 8.18 from the makers, and 8.00 from the sellers.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% Proportion regarding Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable color	8.57	EA	8.57	EA	8.13	VA
2. It has homogenous color	8.27	VA	8.30	VA	8.03	VA
3. It has a golden-brown color	8.23	VA	8.27	VA	8.07	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.36	VA	8.38	VA	8.08	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 30% proportion in terms of its color is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.36 from the consumers, 8.38 from the makers, and 8.08 from the sellers.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% Proportion regarding Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has distinct taste	8.03	VA	8.13	VA	7.97	VA
2. It has a slightly sweet taste	7.87	VA	8.00	VA	7.93	VA
3. It has a well-blended flavor	8.33	VA	8.37	VA	8.17	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.08	VA	8.17	VA	8.02	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 30% proportion in terms of its taste is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.08 from the consumers, 8.17 from the makers, and 8.02 from the sellers.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% Proportion regarding Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a soft texture	8.50	EA	8.67	EA	8.20	VA
2. It can be easily chewed	8.57	EA	8.63	EA	8.30	VA
3. It has a smooth and consistent texture	8.53	EA	8.60	EA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.53	EA	8.63	EA	8.27	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 30% proportion in terms of its texture is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.53 from the consumers and 8.63 from the makers.

Evaluation of Consumers, Sellers, and Makers of the TRIO Pancake Mix For 40% Proportion

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% Proportion regarding Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a distinct appearance.	7.97	VA	8.20	VA	8.27	VA
2. It is free from lumps.	7.93	VA	8.23	VA	8.23	VA
3. It looks tender and easy to bite.	8.57	EA	8.57	EA	8.23	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.16	VA	8.33	VA	8.24	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its appearance is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.16 from the consumers, 8.33 from the makers, and 8.24 from the sellers.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% Proportion regarding Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable aroma	8.50	EA	8.30	VA	8.27	VA
2. It has a sweeter and freshly made smell	8.30	VA	8.33	VA	8.17	VA
3. It has buttery aroma	8.40	VA	8.27	VA	8.27	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.40	VA	8.30	VA	8.23	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its aroma is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.40 from the consumers, 8.30 from the makers, and 8.23 from the sellers.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% Proportion regarding Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable color	8.57	EA	8.70	EA	8.50	EA
2. It has homogenous color	8.37	VA	8.40	VA	8.40	VA
3. It has a golden-brown color	8.40	VA	8.53	EA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.44	VA	8.54	EA	8.40	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its color is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.44 from the consumers, 8.54 from the makers, and 8.40 from the sellers.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% Proportion regarding Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has distinct taste	8.10	VA	8.17	VA	8.10	VA
2. It has a slightly sweet taste	8.00	VA	8.07	VA	8.20	VA
3. It has a well-blended flavor	8.63	EA	8.50	EA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.24	VA	8.24	VA	8.20	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its taste is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.24 from the consumers, 8.24 from the makers, and 8.20 from the sellers.

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% Proportion regarding Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a soft texture	8.53	EA	8.53	EA	8.23	VA
2. It can be easily chewed	8.63	EA	8.57	EA	8.23	VA
3. It has a smooth and consistent texture	8.60	EA	8.53	EA	8.57	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.59	EA	8.54	EA	8.34	VA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its texture is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.59 from the consumers and 8.54 from the makers. From the sellers, the TRIO pancake mix with 40% proportion in terms of its texture is very acceptable with the weighted mean value of 8.34.

Evaluation of Consumers, Sellers, and Makers of the TRIO Pancake Mix For 50% Proportion

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% Proportion regarding Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a distinct appearance.	8.20	VA	8.37	VA	8.63	EA
2. It is free from lumps.	8.03	VA	9.23	EA	8.47	VA
3. It looks tender and easy to bite.	8.60	EA	8.67	EA	8.73	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.28	VA	8.76	EA	8.61	EA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its appearance is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.76 from the makers and 8.61 from the sellers. Moreover, they also said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its appearance is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.28 from the consumers.

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% Proportion regarding Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable aroma.	8.70	EA	8.57	EA	8.60	EA
2. It has a sweeter and freshly made smell	8.43	VA	8.50	EA	8.60	EA
3. It has buttery aroma	8.27	VA	8.33	VA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.47	VA	8.47	VA	8.60	EA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its aroma is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.60 from the sellers. Moreover, they also said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its aroma is very acceptable with the weighted mean value of 8.47 both from the consumers and from the makers.

Table 13. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% Proportion regarding Color

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has an acceptable color	8.47	VA	8.67	EA	8.73	EA
2. It has homogenous color	8.30	VA	8.43	VA	8.80	EA
3. It has a golden-brown color	8.57	EA	8.53	EA	8.73	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.44	VA	8.54	EA	8.76	EA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its color is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.54 from the makers and 8.76 from the sellers.

Moreover, they also said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its color is very acceptable with the weighted mean value of 8.44 from the consumers.

Table 14. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% Proportion regarding Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has distinct taste	8.40	VA	8.47	VA	8.67	EA
2. It has a slightly sweet taste	8.23	VA	8.20	VA	8.63	EA
3. It has a well-blended flavor	8.47	VA	8.53	EA	8.73	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.37	VA	8.40	VA	8.68	EA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its taste is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.68 from the sellers. Moreover, they also said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its taste is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.37 from the consumers and 8.40 from the makers.

Table 15. Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% Proportion regarding Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The TRIO Pancake has a soft texture	8.33	VA	8.47	VA	8.57	EA
2. It can be easily chewed	8.50	EA	8.63	EA	8.60	EA
3. It has a smooth and consistent texture	8.37	VA	8.47	VA	8.73	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.40	VA	8.52	EA	8.63	EA

As a whole, the respondents said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its texture is Extremely Acceptable (EA) with the weighted mean value of 8.52 from the makers and 8.63 from the sellers. Moreover, they also said that the TRIO pancake mix with 50% proportion in terms of its texture is Very Acceptable (VA) with the weighted mean value of 8.40 from the consumers.

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents of the TRIO Pancake Mix Utilizing the Three Different Proportions

Table 16. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 30% Proportion

Criteria	F _{computed} Value	F _{Critical} Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.87	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	1.36	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Color	1.96	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.33	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	2.54	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

The table reveals that the computed F-values of 0.87 for appearance, 1.36 for the aroma, 1.96 for the color, 0.33 for the taste, and 2.54 for the texture are all less than 3.10 critical F-value. This means that at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there are no significant differences in the evaluation of the consumer, maker, and seller respondents of the TRIO pancake mix with a 30% proportion.

Table 17. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 40% Proportion

Criteria	F _{computed} Value	F _{Critical} Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.48	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.50	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Color	0.54	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Taste	0.07	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
e. Texture	1.20	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

The table reveals that the computed F-values of 0.48 for appearance, 0.50 for the aroma, 0.54 for the color, 0.07 for the taste, and 1.20 for the texture are all less than 3.10 critical F-value. This means that at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there are no significant differences in the evaluation of the consumer, maker, and seller respondents of the TRIO pancake mix with a 40% proportion.

The table 18 reveals that the computed F-values of 1.49 for appearance, 0.47 for the aroma, 2.20 for the color, 2.34 for the taste, and 0.88 for the texture are all less than 3.10 critical F-value. This means that at 5% level of significance, the statistical decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there are no significant differences in the evaluation of the consumer, maker, and seller

respondents of the TRIO pancake mix with a 50% proportion.

Table 18. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 50% Proportion*

Criteria	$F_{computed}$ Value	$F_{critical}$ Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	1.49	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.47	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Color	2.20	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
d. Taste	2.34	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
e. Texture	0.88	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

Evaluation of Consumers, Sellers, and Makers in the Production of TRIO Pancake Mix Utilizing the Three Proportions

Table 19. *Summary of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of TRIO Pancake Mix Using 30% Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Supply Availability	4.63	VHP	4.74	VHP	4.33	HP
b. Production Cost	4.73	VHP	4.78	VHP	4.39	HP
c. Consumer Demand	4.71	VHP	4.90	VHP	4.46	HP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.69	VHP	4.81	VHP	4.39	HP

As a whole, the consumer and maker-respondents said that the production of TRIO pancake mix using 30% proportion has a Very High Potential (VHP). Furthermore, the seller-respondents said that the production of TRIO pancake mix using 30% proportion has a High Potential (HP).

Table 20. *Summary of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of TRIO Pancake Mix Using 40% Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Supply Availability	4.69	VHP	4.79	VHP	4.38	HP
b. Production Cost	4.76	VHP	4.84	VHP	4.43	HP
c. Consumer Demand	4.81	VHP	4.89	VHP	4.41	HP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.75	VHP	4.84	VHP	4.41	HP

As a whole, the consumer and maker-respondents said that the production of TRIO pancake mix using 40% proportion has a Very High Potential (VHP). Furthermore, the seller-respondents said that the production of TRIO pancake mix using 40% proportion has a High Potential (HP).

Table 21. *Summary of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of TRIO Pancake Mix Using 50% Proportion*

	Respondents					
	Consumers		Makers		Sellers	
	OWM	VI	OWM	VI	OWM	VI
a. Supply Availability	4.56	VHP	4.78	VHP	4.81	VHP
b. Production Cost	4.64	VHP	4.86	VHP	4.83	VHP
c. Consumer Demand	4.74	VHP	4.87	VHP	4.84	VHP
Grand Weighted Mean	4.65	VHP	4.84	VHP	4.83	VHP

As a whole, the consumer-, maker-, and seller-respondents said that the production of TRIO pancake mix using 50% proportion has a Very High Potential (VHP).

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents in the Production of the TRIO Pancake Mix

The table 22 revealed that the F-values of 5.53 for the supply availability, 5.67 for the production cost, and 8.19 for the consumer demand are all greater than 3.10 critical F-value which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there are significant differences in the evaluations of the consumer-, maker- and seller-respondents in the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 30% proportion regarding supply availability, production cost and consumer demand. This concludes that the respondents' evaluations are not the same.

Table 22. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 30% Proportion*

Criteria	$F_{computed}$ Value	$F_{Critical}$ Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	5.53	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	5.67	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	8.19	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

The table 23 revealed that the F-values of 6.06 for the supply availability, 5.86 for the production cost, and 10.62 for the consumer demand are all greater than 3.10 critical F-value which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there are significant differences in the evaluations of the consumer-, maker- and seller-respondents in the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 40% proportion regarding supply availability, production cost and consumer demand. In consequence, the respondents' evaluations are significantly varied.

Table 23. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 40% Proportion*

Criteria	$F_{computed}$ Value	$F_{Critical}$ Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	6.06	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	5.86	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	10.62	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

The table 24 reveals that the F-value of 3.37 for the supply availability is greater than 3.10 critical F-value which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that there is a significant difference in the evaluations of the consumer-, maker- and seller-respondents in the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% proportion regarding supply availability. On the other hand, the F-values of 2.04 for the production cost and 0.90 for the consumer demand are both less than 3.10 critical F-value which leads to the failure to reject the null hypothesis. This means that there are no significant differences in the evaluations of the consumer-, maker- and seller-respondents in the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix with 50% proportion regarding production cost and consumer demand.

Table 24. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations in the Production of the TRIO Pancake Mix Using 50% Proportion*

Criteria	$F_{computed}$ Value	$F_{Critical}$ Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	3.37	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
b. Production Cost	2.04	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant
c. Consumer Demand	0.90	3.10	Reject the H_0	Significant

Comments and suggestions given by the respondents to improve the product

The comments provided by the three groups of respondents regarding the evaluation of TRIO Pancake Mix are the following: a) The pancake tastes balanced and delicious, it has the right amount of sweetness; no syrup is needed; b) It has a buttery aroma, and it has soft and fluffy texture; c) Of the three, the 50% pancake mixture had the best flavor; d) The added ingredients complement each other. You can taste the sweet potato and jackfruit seeds, which add a nice touch of flavor to the pancake; e) It has healthy ingredients that are good for the body; f) It is a good concept and innovative idea; g) Highly recommended, ready for market.

The suggestions provided by the three groups of respondents to improve the production of the TRIO Pancake Mix are the following: a) The pancake will taste better if it is sweeter; b) 50% mixture has the best taste but it should be improved, it has lumps; c) Lessen the other ingredients, the taste of milk is overpowering.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, the researcher concluded the following:

Innovating a standard recipe, specifically a pancake mix, can be done with the use of jackfruit seeds, sweet potato, and taro flours as substitute for wheat flour.

Physicochemical analysis indicate that the pancake made of TRIO Pancake Mix is healthy and safe for consumption.

With the results of the evaluation by the respondents, all three mixtures (i.e., 30%, 40%, 50%) of TRIO pancake mix are acceptable with regards to appearance, color, aroma, taste, texture.

All respondents share a common positive response regarding aforementioned criteria among the different proportions (i.e., 30%, 40%, 50%) of the pancake made of TRIO Pancake Mix. Specifically, higher proportions of the mixture were deemed of better quality by the respondents.

The product shows high potential for its production cost, supply availability, and consumer demand, with higher proportions of the mixture being more favorable to all respondents. Therefore, the product is highly acceptable in terms of the aforementioned criteria.

All respondents shared a common positive response to the prepared pancake mix. Comments by some respondents included preference for sweeter pancakes, lesser lumps in the pancake texture, and lesser use of milk in the mixture.

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